

Deliverable D6.11

Pilot (PT) Technical report and achieved results (2 | 2)

Deliverable report

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Disclaimer

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DIGIECOQUARRY project is fully concerned about the potential social risks that may arise as a consequence of the project's activities. For this reason, a dedicated Work Package (**WP7 - Mechanisms for social acceptance & interaction with policymakers**) is active since the beginning of the project identifying, analysing and monitoring social risks in each of the project sites. Main social risks have been already analysed and classified in deliverables 7.1 and 7.2, including also potential risks of DIGIECOQUARRY technologies' deployment beyond the end of the project. The identification and classification of social risks allow **a close follow-up of the main potential negative impacts in society to avoid them throughout the whole project activities**. Among potential social risks, the impact on the workforce is monitored with specific attention to ensure full adaptation of workers to new working technologies and processes and avoid job destruction.

To ensure a successful implementation of the developed technologies in the pilot sites, social risks identified in WP7 for each pilot have been carefully considered. WP6 also includes the assessment and monitoring of relevant KPIs, which will help reduce the risk of work accidents and minimize the environmental impact.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DoA	Description of Action
EB	Exploitation Board
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement
RP	Reporting Period
PRC	Project Research Committee
WP	Work Package

1 Pilot overview

AGREPOR is a Portuguese aggregates producer with 10 active quarries and owned by the major Portuguese cement producer CIMPOR.

AGREPOR has a wide variety of quarries (granite, limestone, dolomite and gypsum) and supplies a wide variety of public and private customers that operate for instance in public works, RMC, fertilizers, lime production, cement, concrete, ballast, mortar, etc.

Agrepur pilot site is Alenquer quarry that is located near Lisbon, extracted limestone, with a crushing and screening plant for aggregates production. The crushing and screening plant is subject to the implementations provided by DigiEcoQuarry.

- Models for quarry operations.
- Devices for automation of the treatment plant.
- Monitoring sensors and analysis tools for mobile machinery.
- BIM.
- Artificial Intelligence algorithms.
- H&S technologies.
- Environmental simulation platform.

Figure 1 View of CIMPOR's Alenquer quarry plant.

In CIMPOR's site, the autonomous and intelligent system for aggregates transportation from crushing to stock, storage and external transport traceability (KTA3.1&3.2) will be implemented with the focus on rationalising energy consumption and using equipment. Main areas monitored will be levels of the silos, analysis of the stock zone for prioritisation on transport, remote and autonomous interpretation of storage locations. The installation of technologies that enable an autonomous management will allow prioritising the aggregates to be transported, optimising routes, transport speed and deposition sites with all security safeguards, validating and demonstrating these DigiEcoQuarry solutions.

For external transport, the validation of the technologies that enable full traceability from the quarry to the customer will be demonstrated by ensuring route optimisation in terms of the best possible route that minimises transportation time and fuel consumption, Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) and communication to customer and quarry (dispatch), sharing of inter-fleet information to adjust the travel speed and to guarantee just-in-time in congested unloading sites. Other aspects that will be validated in terms of storage to external transport connection will be the correct identification of the aggregate to be loaded, silo discharge control, correct truck positioning without spilling and cargo viability and communication to driver.

From IT point of view, Platform design has been implemented (WP4 – KTA 4.3), BIM models (WP4 – KTA 4.1) and AI algorithms (WP4 – KTA 4.2) as well as H&S & environmental system management (WP5 – KTA 5 and KTA 6).

It is important to mention that Deliverable D6.5 will be used as a reference together with the WP3 and WP4 deliverables in order not to repeat the contents.

2 Implementation of technologies

At the beginning of July 2022, the activities carried out in Alenquer pilot sites have consisted mainly in the acquisition of data coming from 11 sensors and 2 cameras installed until now in the mobile equipment. This allows to create a more structured and consisting of database representing a data history, monitoring the performance of mobile equipment (e.g. number of loads, downtime, etc..).

At the end of June 2023, the scales were installed in the conveyor belts. Once integrated into SCADA, this system will help us to monitor and optimize the crushing plant.

2.1 Definition of requirements and characteristics of the data inputs (Task 3.1)

This task entails the identification of all the sources for inputs and outputs in the quarry processes. Agrepor has been working with partners providing inputs and relevant information to proceed with the needed development.

2.2 Development of sensors, automation, and process control (Task 3.2)

2.2.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Arco Mineral Platinum Control Software
Overview	In a quarry, sensor control is used to monitor and control various variables and processes related to the extraction and handling of materials. The control of these sensors can be done through a SCADA system or an industrial automation system. These systems collect data from sensors in real time, allowing operators to monitor key variables, receive alarms, and make adjustments or take action as needed. In addition, the
Key Components	<p>For the correct control of the quarries, various control equipment is used to monitor and control the operating processes such as programmable logic controllers (PLC), SCADA systems, management software, sensors and actuators, among others.</p> <p>In the case of CIMPOR, the supply includes 8 weighing systems, 2 metal detectors and the automation of the existing sensors in the pilot plant.</p> <p>All of it is distributed in two different locations. On the one hand, the control room where 3 weighing systems are controlled with their corresponding AE-9220V2 equipment and where the SCADA of the plant is displayed and controlled through a monitor.</p>

	On the other hand, the loading room, where the 5 remaining weighing systems for truck loading control are controlled with the AE-9220V2 equipment.
Target Audience	The main target is companies in the mining and construction sectors. Quarries, aggregate processing plants, etc.
Hardware Requirements	<p>COMPUTER REQUIREMENTS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Intel Core i3 processor or higher. - 4GB RAM or higher. - Windows 10 Professional 64-bit operating system. - 22" monitor or higher with 1920x1080 resolution. - 240GB SSD hard drive. - Connections: 2 Ethernet network cards. <p>REMOTE ACCESS REQUIREMENTS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ADSL line + Fixed IP address.
Installation Process	Installation of Arco control equipment that communicates with the plant's existing control and power cabinet. All signals are communicated so they can be displayed on the SCADA and monitored and controlled.
Communication Protocols	Communication via TCP/IP protocol with PLCs (Siemens, Schneider, Allen Bradley)
Data Storage & Management	Once the data is collected, it is stored on Arco's servers. Once received, the data is stored, processed, and integrated into the reporting system. All data is stored in our cloud system and is protected by regulatory compliance policies and backups.
AI Integration & Implementation	Models used with AI for machine learning and deep learning are being developed and incorporated into a testing phase.
Application Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SCADA developed with the SIMAR305 library. - Easy to use with mouse and keyboard. - Multi-station capability via local network connection. - User-configurable lists with printing options.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Machine alarms. - Preventive machine maintenance. - Import/export of files to other management systems: Excel, Access, ASCII, etc. - Access restrictions via user-configurable passwords, easy to program using groups. - Actions on machines via mouse. - Connection to Siemens, Schneider, Eaton Möeller PLCs, etc. - Connection to AE-9220 or AE-9228 continuous weighing equipment for production control. - Arco environment. - Program for controlling an aggregates plant that manages up to 128 digital I/Os.
Security & Compliance	Hardware protected against unauthorized access and cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data.
Performance Metrics	<p>Real-time process visualization</p> <p>Production log</p> <p>Operating hours</p> <p>Number of starts</p> <p>History</p> <p>Alert configuration</p> <p>Reports on production, consumption, alarms, and maintenance</p> <p>Management of groups, users, and access permissions</p> <p>Representation of process values in a graphic curve</p> <p>View instantaneous values and archived values</p>
Support & Maintenance	Technical support, training, and assistance, both on-site and remote. KPI monitoring integration into various reporting systems. Sales, upselling, and marketing activities for commercialization.
Business Model & Pricing	Arco Mineral Platinum Software pricing is based on various scalable and integrated projects. Each project has its own unique characteristics and the machinery/sensor technology to be integrated.
Competitive Advantage	Arco Mineral Platinum Software is unique and developed exclusively by ARCO. It is a solution for monitoring and

	controlling plants or quarries that can be installed with minimal production downtime. Remote or on-site support is almost immediate, helping the end user in the event of any incident.
Future Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvements to the graphical process Improvement of AI algorithms Integration of new KPIs Improvement of the reporting system and its export

2.2.2 Activities performed since Novembre 2023

Since the fourth quarter of 2023, ARCO has implemented the eight weighing systems, as well as their respective control cabinets, using AE-9220V2 equipment. It has also implemented SCADA with a monitor for viewing. The Arco Mineral Platinum software is operational and functioning correctly.

Figure 2 - Integrated belt weighing system.

Figure 3 - Encoder speed meter.

Figure 4 - Platinum Mineral Arch Software and AE-9220V2 equipment in Control Room.

Figure 5 - AE-9220V2 equipment in the loading room.

2.3 Monitoring sensors and analysing tools for mobile machinery (Task 3.3)

2.3.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	MEMT [Mobile Equipment Monitoring Tool]
Overview	The development of MEMT is based on the state of improving the productivity and the performance of the mining equipment. The solution, based on self-developed, OEM independent hardware and ML – AI reporting system helps to capture, analyze & report different mobile machinery KPIs.
Key Components	Hardware: Self-developed plug and play sensor unit mounted in any type of machinery Software: AI-ML reporting system able to monitor & report performance and production KPIs
Target Audience	Industry: Mining & construction industry. Main targets: Mine managers, mining experts, continuous performance managers and mining companies in general in need of a digital solution for monitoring the machinery performance

Hardware Requirements	about Edge sensor unit & internet connection
Installation Process	Plug and play solution that can be installed in 10min in the mobile machinery without the need of accessing the CanBUS of the mobile machinery or without the need of any retrofit kit. The Edge device can be installed at any position in the cabin of the mobile equipment. It contains an antenna that needs to be orientated to the sky. The sensor unit can be connected to the electrical supply via a 12/24V socket in the cabin or to any other power source..
Communication Protocols -	Data transmission based on terrestrial communication [2G – 3G – 4G – 5G]
Data Storage & Management	The data, once collected by the sensor unit, is transmitted to the servers of about via TC. Once received, the data is stored, processed and integrated in the reporting system. All the data is stored in our cloud system and secure via compliance considerations and backups.
AI Integration & Implementation	AI models based on, machine learning, deep learning, neuronal networks and AI algorithms that detect automatically the different machinery activities. The different activities are integrated in the reporting system according to the different KPIs to report.
Application Features	User interface with access to the reporting system. The different modules of the reporting system are: Production and productivity Fleet efficiency Mine organization & Machinery availability Idle times & inefficiencies Communication and reporting
Security & Compliance	Compliance with European standards in a matter of GDPR. Hardware protected against accessing and Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data.
Performance Metrics	Time to login to the platform Access and refresh of the dashboard Update ratio of the platform Integration of the KPIs

Support & Maintenance	Technical support, training and assistance. Also, integration of monitoring KPIs at different reporting systems. Sales, up selling and marketing activities for commercialization.
Business Model & Pricing	SaaS model with the possibility of paying-as-you-go based on different scalable and integrated modular product. Each module has its price and all the modules can be integrated or purchase as standalone features or being combined for having the full monitoring system capabilities
Competitive Advantage	The unique and modular system of about is completely OEM independent. In addition, it is a plug & solution that can be installed without the necessity of sending the machine to the workshop. The installation could be done in 10minutes by the local team and is Can Bus independent. In addition, for accessing the platform there is no special need or requirement just a normal internet connection.
Future Enhancements	Integration of the camera system for detecting different activities Enhancement of the AI algorithms Integration of new KPIs Enhancement of the reporting system

2.3.2 Activities performed since Novembre 2023

Since Q4 2023, About has integrated a new dashboard system. This dashboard system has been integrated after contacting the pilot site and making it according to their operational needs. In SiteView, the new filtering system is available and recording all the activities related to the transports and number of cycles.

In Figure 6 it is possible to observe how the new filtering is divided by:

- Location: all locations Loading locations, unloading locations and combined locations [from- to]

- Machinery: loading machinery & transport machinery

Figure 6 SiteView - Mass flow.

In addition, it is possible to have the full transport list and download it for further reporting [see Figure 7].

The screenshot displays a detailed table of transport records. The table has the following columns: Start loading, Loader, Transport device type, License plate/Identifier, Loading location/Material, Unloading location, Type, and Tonnage. The data shows multiple entries for rigid dumptrucks, all with a tonnage of 60.0, used for 'Crusher feeding' at 'Exploitation permit 4659'.

Start loading	Loader	Transport device type	License plate/Identifier	Loading location/Material	Unloading location	Type	Tonnage
03/13/2025 11:38:14	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	Cat775G 850	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 11:34:29	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	HD605-8 (35815)	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 11:14:46	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	Cat775G 850	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 11:10:57	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	HD605-8 (35815)	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 10:51:11	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	Cat775G 850	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 10:47:03	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	HD605-8 (35815)	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 10:28:30	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	Cat775G 850	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 10:22:34	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	HD605-8 (35815)	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 10:02:29	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	Cat775G 850	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 09:57:48	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	HD605-8 (35815)	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 09:29:57	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	HD605-8 (35815)	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0
03/13/2025 09:26:43	Volvo L350H (2055)	Rigid dumptruck	Cat775G 850	Exploitation permit 4659	Crusher feeding	↔	60.0

Figure 7 Transports table.

Some other KPIs integrated in the platform are the ones related to the cycle times and distance driven as shown in Figure 8. This fast and fast integration of KPIs helps the mining responsible person to check the production levels of their operation according to their planning and to follow the most relevant information by just doing few clicks.

Figure 8 Cycle times and t/km.

Important here to mention are the KPIs related to the machinery utilization. These KPIs have been integrated thanks to the improvement of the idling classifier [see Figure 9]. This information can help to understand the overall fleet activities and the machinery utilization [percentage working vs percentage idling].

Figure 9 Machinery utilization.

2.4 ICT Platform design and implementation (Task 4.2)

The ICT platform in fact is not specific to a given quarry. In D4.2, titled “Report on IQS Design and Architecture,” the design and architecture of the Intelligent Quarrying System (IQS), developed by AKKODIS, are described. The implementation of this architecture and site’s specific development were described in D4.6 “Report on IQS, Services Integration and deployment”. Hence, more details could be found as follow:

- The IQS components currently deployed, their main functions and availability for each pilot site, are described in section 3.1 of D4.3.
- The Centralized data management platform and the CDMF front-end are described in section 3.2 of D4.3
- Transport service, Plant production service, Environmental data management service, Health and safety service are described in section 3.2.3 of D4.6.
- Business management tools Section 3.4 of D4.6.
- The data lake, the databases, the IoT platform and Talend integration are described respectively in section 3.2.4, 3.2.5, 3.2.6 and 3.2.7 of D4.6.
- The data connectors are described in section 3.3 of D4.6.

The following 4 figures show the front-end welcome page, the Shared data screen, the plant production screen, and the Data Lake / IoT screen created for CIMPOR.

Figure 10: CDMF Front-End: Welcome page – “Home” screen.

Figure 11: CDMF Front-End – “Shared Data” screen.

Figure 12: CDMF Front-End – “Plant production” screen.

Figure 13: CDMF Front-End – “Data Lake / IoT” screen.

Several quarry processes (Production, Transport, Automation, Environment, H&S, IoT for AI Service) have been implemented within the IQS, and their data models have been defined. Connections using REST APIs have been created, enabling direct communication for data exchange between the expert systems and the IQS according to a newly defined common data format.

The data integration process has been implemented, with data flowing at varying frequencies (hourly, daily, monthly) based on the use case. Integration was achieved using a proxy design pattern, adopted by all site data providers, to push

data from SCADA (Arco), Transport (Abaut), H&S (ITK) and PlantSmith systems to the IQS, and to enable data consumers to pull data from the IQS.

For IoT use cases, after deploying IoT sensors (for dust and water) by Sigma, the generated data is collected, stored in the DEQ IoT platform, and made accessible to the Forecast AI Service via the IQS data lake browser service. In this scenario, sensors utilizing LoRa technology are integrated into the IQS by connecting The Things Network (TTN), which leverages the LoRaWAN network protocol, to the Azure IoT platform. This illustrates the DEQ platform's robust capability to seamlessly integrate with any IoT sensors.

The results list of the IQS data integration within the project, including the data availability status in the data lake across all sites, is detailed in Section 4 of D4.6.

In addition to the reporting tools provided by the expert systems, the IQS leveraged the Power BI ecosystem to create comprehensive dashboards and reports that provide insights into KPIs from different facets of quarrying. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring. The dashboards are described in section 4.3 of D4.2 and in section 3 of D4.6.

All the dashboards created for CIMPOR are accessible in one power-bi application accessible to pilot site's users as shown in next figure.

Figure 14: DEQ Power BI App for CIMPOR

2.5 AI algorithms (Task 4.3): Forecast service

Sigma in collaboration with the UPM-AI group have been intensively working in the design of an AI-centred service to provide valuable information to the CIMPOR quarry related to the very complex set of variables that intervene in the production of the material and on the day-to-day business. An important effort was put on the quest for information sources that could be easily available (Publicly or by specific agreements). At the end it was decided to setup an IOT network (based on the LoRa networking solution) at the ALENQUER quarry to obtain from the field real time values that could help the quarry on their decision-making process. In fact, the following type of sensors were chosen:

- **Dust sensors:** a commercial solution, quite expensive, that has driven the decision to implement at SIGMA an ad-hoc design. So, at the end, two types of sensors are being used and deployed. The need of several sensors arose from the fact that the quarry occupies a large area and it is important to sense the dust. In order to understand the need of spraying water (consumption and costs) over the quarry roads and also with respect to the pollution that may affect the population on the neighbouring cities.

- **A weather station:** giving information about the wind direction, temperature and humidity. The latter information combined with production information generated by ARCO’s weighting system is being used to provide insights about the production timings.
- **Water consumption counters:** They are used to measure how much water is consumed from the public infrastructure. For CIMPOR it is key to know if they can adapt measures to consume less and predict when the consumption will surpass the allowed thresholds before having to pay “excessive water consumption” bonuses to the utility in charge.

In the design of the service three main goals were pursued:

1. Minimize the amount of water used to mitigate the dust generated in the quarry.
2. Optimize the production rate considering the meteorological conditions and the past production history.
3. Estimate the periods when the plant can operate using a high percentage of clean energy.

In the following sections a table summarizing the features of the implemented AI forecast service is presented. Then the activities performed since the delivery of the previous related deliverable D6.5 “Pilot (PT) Technical report and achieved results (1|2)” are summarized.

2.5.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	Production and Consumption Forecast
Overview	<p>The forecast AI service has basically included the following analysis areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water consumption analysis obtaining input from the water consumption sensors Dust pollution analysis over the quarry grounds obtained also with the dust sensor outputs Electricity consumption analysis obtained from the internet (https://www.omie.es/es/file-download?parents%5b0%5d=marginalpdbc&filename=marginalpdbc_%5bYYYYMMDD%5d.1) (https://www.omie.es/pt/market-results/monthly/daily-market/hourly-market?scope=monthly&year=2023&month=1&data=8) Production analysis that includes information from the weather public service in Portugal (link: https://api.ipma.pt/open-data/observation/meteorology/stations/observations.json) <p>This data is combined to generate different outputs devoted to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduce water consumption based on a prediction made with the consumption data available obtained from the installed sensors. The prediction takes as input all the historic data that is captured to model the consumption tendency in a year. Analyze the production history to help the quarry managers understand what measures to take to increase productivity by predicting and advising when the productivity will be better in the near future. The model considers the weather history and the related production figures. Recommend in terms of the energy costs historically, which dates would be more effective to produce reducing energy costs linked to the clean energy being handled on the energy utility network. <p>The models being employed take as input IoT sensor values, equipment in the CIMPOR plant (Scale values) and web-based information.</p>

<p>Key Components</p>	<p>In the following diagram the key components are represented for the Forecast service at CIMPOR:</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Figure 15. High level component diagram of the forecast service</i></p> <p>The service components are here clearly shown and they could be classified in the following fashion:</p> <p>Left hand side top, there are two blocks one where all the physical sensors are included that were installed at the quarry. The communication technology chosen is LoRa wireless technology that is now an industry standard and is demonstrating to be very reliable and easy to set up. The data then from Alenquer is sent via a 4G network to the IQS (IoT Platform, Datalake and DWH), the AI models run in cloud servers at Sigma and data is sent back to the DWH using Internet protocols. The 4G network employed is the same one as employed in Valdilechas’s Cemex quarry, the Movistar IoT network.</p> <p>On the left-hand side bottom, the external information systems accessed via internet are listed and already mentioned above.</p> <p>IQS components featuring, the IoT platform that is responsible to process the incoming sensor data, and the Datalake which gets the data from the expert systems. In this case the production information, the belt weighting system information. Finally, the AI algorithms that run on specialized servers which analyze the information introduced into the DWH following specific patterns that are easier to analyze. The results are fed back to the DWH in order to be used on the designed dashboards that are shown and explained later on in this table.</p>
<p>Target Audience</p>	<p>This service is aimed at helping the quarry managers and operators to get insights on very important variables such as water consumption, dust pollution, production data, influence of external variables by combining all this information and extracting attractive prediction and forecast analysis.</p>
<p>Hardware Requirements</p>	<p>Sensors: they should be and are LoRaWAN compatible meaning that they hold the relevant certificates and are compatible with the networking technology that enables important networking functionalities such as registration, authentication and discovery.</p> <p>LoRaWAN gateway that enables local connectivity in this case on the quarry grounds allowing long distances between the devices. In fact, it may reach distances around 15 and 20 Kms.</p> <p>Cloud infrastructure to host the IQS components. AZURE and Google cloud components are included in the project solution.</p>
<p>Installation Process</p>	<p>The local installation process had to count with the quarry operators’ active participation but not implying complicated installation procedures. Only the LoRa Gateway had to be placed nearby a</p>

power source. The rest of the sensors are fed with a battery expecting to last about 5 years before having to replace it. The sensors had to be mounted on a pole. They are strategically placed around the quarry grounds to ensure a good coverage to measure, for instance, how the dust is propagating in almost all directions. To set up the connections between all elements it is not needed to be physically in the quarry, it can be done remotely, in fact in most cases the SIGMA team stayed in the Madrid offices.

A map of the quarry is bellow attached, showing the placement of the different elements of the IoT network.

Figure 16. Installation map of all The IOT network elements of the Forecast service.

Communication Protocols -

Two types of networks are used: a LoRaWAN network and GSM-4G network to transmit the data to the IQS. It was clear from the very beginning that the local networks from the quarry could not be used for security reasons.

The main characteristics of the LoRaWAN network are here summarized:

1. Long Range
 - LoRaWAN supports communication over distances of up to 15 km in rural areas and 2-5 km in urban environments.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It uses sub-GHz frequencies (e.g., 868 MHz in Europe, 915 MHz in the U.S.), allowing for better penetration through obstacles. <p>2. Low Power Consumption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN devices can operate on small batteries for years (often 5-10 years) due to their low power requirements. • It uses duty cycling and adaptive data rate (ADR) to optimize energy efficiency. <p>3. Low Data Rate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports data rates between 0.3 kbps to 50 kbps, making it suitable for small, intermittent data transmissions. <p>4. Star Topology (Gateway-Based)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN networks use a star-of-stars topology where end nodes communicate with central gateways. • Gateways relay data between end devices and the network server via IP-based backhaul (e.g., cellular, Ethernet, or WiFi). <p>5. License-Free Spectrum</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operates in unlicensed ISM bands (e.g., 868 MHz in Europe, 915 MHz in the U.S.). <p>6. High Scalability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supports thousands to millions of nodes per network and support for multiple gateways. <p>7. Security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uses AES-128 encryption at multiple layers. <p>9. Supports Bidirectional Communication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Uplink communication (sensor data to gateway). • Downlink communication (control commands to devices). • Supports confirmed and unconfirmed messages. <p>10. Geolocation Capabilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LoRaWAN allows network-based geolocation without GPS by measuring signal time differences across gateways. • Useful for tracking assets and mobile applications. <p>All these details are here included since this technology has shown to be an excellent choice for an industrial environment in remote locations as a quarry. As for the 4G cellular network employed, it is a very standard solution supported by the solution offered by Telefonica Movistar IoT network ensuring a dedicated network for industrial applications replicating the key elements of the commercial network solution. It supports up to 1Gbps speeds with a low latency of 50ms.</p>
<p>Data Storage & Management</p>	<p>The solution has no servers on site. All communications, device management and data transfers are governed by the LoRaWAN protocols and management interface. Data is finally stored and processed by the IQS elements: IoT platform, Datalake and the Data warehouse. All details can be found in WP4 deliverables.</p>

- AI Analysis components:
 - Water Consumption Analysis block takes as consideration the time, the values of the counter sensors, the threshold set by the water utility that serves the Alenquer quarry. The analysis provides a forecast of when the actual consumption of the quarry will reach the mentioned threshold and a prediction of the overall consumption in a year's time.
 - Dust Generation Analysis block, on the one hand provides real time dust figures considering the measurements on all sensors deployed at the quarry. And, on the other, stores the detected values to relate them to the water consumption values. The latter is so, since monitored water consumption is only used to spray the quarry roads to avoid excessive dust concentration putting in risk the health of the workers.
 - Electricity Consumption Analysis block, it takes the data coming from the OMIE and relates them to the weather giving recommendation on when to produce at a low electricity cost.
- The Production Analysis block is responsible for the processing of the production figures from the quarry in order to predict future production figures based on the weather information and the past production analysis.

The Consumption and Production Forecast service has as main objective to provide to the quarry manager and operators a tool to visually observe different parameters and values obtained through data modelling, in the form of three different dashboards. The first one combines the analysis of dust pollution on the different points measured in the quarry (dust sensors) together with the wind, temperature and humidity information on the site; a second part of the dashboard shows the water consumption levels showing actual figures and a forecast of the future consumption together with the date when the water threshold set by the water utility is reached.

The second dashboard shows a couple of graphs analyzing the production history and giving insights on when in the future it is advisable to produce at recommended levels taking into consideration weather information predictions.

Finally, the third one illustrates the energy prices analysis based on given time periods and a heat map using as inputs the energy predicted costs on an hourly basis to allow the quarry managers to make decisions on the production profiles and activities to perform. The dashboards that were created are shown below:

Application Features

Figure 18. Dust and water consumption dashboard.

Figure 19. Production efficiency dashboard

Figure 20. Energy cost and production dashboard.

<p>Security & Compliance</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cybersecurity measures to protect hardware and data. - Compliance with industry regulations (GDPR, HIPAA, etc.). <p>No personal data is involved in this AI service and certainly images are not obtained by any means. The LoRaWAN provides a very secure networking environment for the IoT network involving also advanced encryption of the information.</p>
<p>Performance Metrics</p>	<p>KPIs to measure success (e.g., system uptime, AI model accuracy, data processing speed).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Throughput uptime that in this case represents how good has the system performed during a working shift at the plant in terms of up time. Until now it reaches almost 100%. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> $\text{Throughput uptime} = \frac{\text{Total hours AI system uptime}}{\text{Time period}}$ • Prediction Accuracy that measures how well the system infers the water consumption, the costs relative to energy to produce the material in CIMPOR ▪ Mean time between failures that measures the average time the system operates before a failure occurs. Until now the system has been operating for more than 18 months and some HW problems were registered on the quality of the “home made” dust sensors specially at

	<p>the beginning. Now they are stable and functioning well since months and the commercial elements have not registered any failure.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operator intervention rate that measures how often human operators need to intervene to reactivate the service. As mentioned above a couple of times the dust sensors had to be returned to SIGMA for repair. Now that the problems were solved, no intervention has been needed in the last 3 or four months.
<p>Support & Maintenance</p>	<p>The HW maintenance needed in the long run is only devoted to the replacement of batteries on the sensors. For the SW during this stage of the project continuous improvements have been performed on the AI algorithms and models to make the predictions more accurate and ensure that the data pipelines are behaving as expected on the data management processes. The SW maintenance is performed by the service providers that in the case of the projects are basically SIGMA and Akkodis for the IQS components.</p>
<p>Business Model & Pricing</p>	<p>Subscription-based, pay-per-use, or one-time purchase pricing models.</p> <p>The key elements of the business model are the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customer segments: The service is aimed at quarrying sites or other industrial environments that require process or environment monitoring, such as automotive or farming industries. 2. Value proposition: The innovation fills the need of monitoring parameters or processes that were not monitored before, and to unveil new information from the available data. 3. Channels: Direct sales via interviews of commercial team with IT departments. Use of Sigma’s web channel and commercial offices in Madrid, London and Miami. 4. Customer relationships: Personalized assistance fitting to customer’s needs. 5. Revenue streams: Initial installation fee (depending on the type and number of sensors that need to be deployed) plus an annual license fee for data storage and processing services. O&M fee. 6. Key resources: Human resources: field installers, data analysts, hardware specialists, IT personnel, mining engineers. Computation resources: cloud storage, servers for data processing. 7. Key activities: Monitoring, data analysis, process improvement. 8. Key partners: Potentially with hardware providers for developing ad-hoc sensors. 9. Cost structure: Human resources for development, O&M resources, servers (storage and processing), sensor hardware, marketing resources. <p>Given the complexity of the technologies developed by the company, commercial management and technical management always go hand in hand, both in Sigma's beginnings and today, when defining the sales strategy for the commercialization of a new product. As a guideline, the following revenue model is established, although it will have to be adjusted according to the knowledge acquired in the pilot, and after a more in-depth analysis of market potential.</p> <p>Furthermore, due to the open nature of the service, its cost will highly depend on the number of sensors deployed and the information that should be generated.</p> <p>Thus, the pricing of the service will account for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial requirements analysis: interviews with the customer to determine service goals and hardware requirements: 1.000 - 2.000 €.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deployment fee: fixed 2.000 € fee plus 500 € per sensor (depending on the type of sensor, the price might increase). - Additional functionalities: 1.000 – 3.000 € each. - O&M fee: 3.000 € annually.
<p>Competitive Advantage</p>	<p>How this service stands out compared to competitors.</p> <p>The Internet of Things market is expected to grow significantly in the coming years. It was valued at USD 595.73 billion in 2023, with a projected growth from USD 714.48 billion in 2024 to USD 4,062.34 billion by 2032, which represents a CAGR of 24.3% during the forecast period.</p> <p>From a regional perspective, the North American market is expected to be the largest-growing IoT market, thanks, in part, to the deployment of connected vehicles, smart energy projects, home automation and smart manufacturing. However, the Asian-Pacific and European markets are also expected to grow, due to an increase in adoption of IoT technologies for the former, and smart cities and industrial automation for the latter.</p> <p><i>Figure 21 North America IoT Market Size. (2019-2032)</i></p> <p>Turning the focus to the quarrying industry, different players can be found. For instance, Adroit (https://adroit.nz/quarry-monitoring/) or Rayven (https://www.rayven.io/iot-solutions/iot-quarry-solution) offer environment monitoring solutions for quarries, to aid in compliance or Health & Safety.</p> <p>Also worth mentioning are industrial manufacturers for quarrying equipment, who are including IoT capabilities to their products. Examples of this are Komatsu or Caterpillar, who is including sensors to their machines to improve the efficiency and sustainability of their operations.</p>
<p>Future Enhancements</p>	<p>The AI modelling can be further improved in the future in several directions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changing the models involved using Deep neural networks considering then the importance of the data and the training procedures. - Including more variables in the models for production: for example, data of electrical consumption of the crushers involved in the production and/or other machines that may be key for the production (Sieves, conveyor belts, etc.).

2.5.2 Activities performed since Novembre 2023

By November 2023, testing of the dust sensors had been finalized, but the system had not been deployed yet. Thus, the following activities have been carried out since then:

- Hardware:
 - Installation of dust sensors: all four sensors, along with the LoRa gateway, were delivered to CIMPOR representatives during the Lisbon Consortium Meeting in November 2023, and installed by them in the quarry shortly after.
 - Installation of water counters: two water counters were installed by Sigma during a visit to the quarry in April 2024.
 - Installation of weather station: the weather station was sent via courier to the quarry in June 2024 and installed in the quarry shortly after its reception.
 - Maintenance of dust sensors: as has been mentioned, some of the dust sensors stopped sending data at different points during this period, requiring manual intervention. They were revised during the visit to install the water counters, they had to be sent back via courier and fixed in Sigma's office, and one last time during an ad-hoc visit in October 2024. They have been stable since that last visit.
- Data acquisition:
 - Connected to OMIE's and IPMA's APIs to retrieve electricity prices and weather data respectively, and stored those data in the Data Warehouse.
 - Contacted Alenquer municipality to obtain data from a weather station located near the quarry.
 - Created pipelines to retrieve production data from the Datalake.
- Models: analyzed obtained data and developed models for water consumption estimation, production efficiency and clean energy consumption.
- Dashboards: created PowerBI dashboards, with DEQ's look and feel, to present the results of the developed models.

2.6 Integration BIM (Task 4.4)

2.6.1 General Summary

Building Information Modeling (BIM) strategies were implemented at Cimpor to create digital representations of the quarry and treatment plant, enhancing visualization and management. This involved developing 3D models of visible plant assets and topography using drone data, photos, and process schemes. A long-term 4D BIM simulation was created with Asta Powerproject, visualizing the documentation and exploitation phases adapted to the site's specific operational characteristics, including dredging and conveyor-based material transport. Furthermore, a 7D model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) was established using Autodesk Tandem, integrating the BIM model with static asset information and dynamic plant production data retrieved from the project's DataLake via a custom integrator, providing a valuable platform for asset monitoring.

2.6.2 Activities performed since November 2023

Following the initial development reported in Deliverable D4.5, the activities for Cimpor Agrepor-Alenquer focused on finalizing and deploying the BIM tools:

- **BIM Model Finalization:** The 3D BIM models representing the treatment plant and site topography, developed from available site data, were finalized and prepared in IFC format for integration.

- **4D BIM Plan Finalization:** The long-term 4D BIM plan visualizing the documentation and exploitation phases, tailored to the site's dredging and conveyor operations, was completed within Asta Powerproject.
- **CDE Deployment and Data Integration:** The Common Data Environment (CDE) platform using Autodesk Tandem was deployed for Cimpor. This involved uploading the finalized BIM model, incorporating static asset data, and successfully establishing integration with the central DataLake using the custom data integrator. This allowed for the visualization of available dynamic Plant Production data linked to the corresponding assets within the CDE.
- **Training and Handover:** The Cimpor team received access to the CDE platform, along with initial guidance on utilizing its features for visualizing the plant and the integrated operational data.

2.7 Development of H&S systems for stationary equipment (Task 5.1 and 5.2)

2.7.1 General Summary

Section	Description
Service Name	AI based Person detection System
Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CIMPOR expressed interest in monitoring a specific area of their site where vehicle movement and personnel interaction posed a collision risk. - The system architecture and the corresponding system features are displayed in figure xx below. It is based on improving safety by informing about critical situations.
Key Components	The components are laid out in Deliverable 5.1
Target Audience	Different stakeholders will benefit from this solution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Workers working in hazardous situations will be informed. - Operators who get a report about the amount of hazardous situations reported.
Hardware Requirements	The hardware is described in Deliverable 5.1
Installation Process	As we set-up different field of views, depending on the site requirements, we need to be present at the site to support our partners.
Communication Protocols	Based on Cellular network (3G)
Data Storage & Management	Except for the number of person detection in IQS, we do not store any data.

AI Integration & Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For this use case, only AI makes sense, as it is much more performant than classical algorithms (see also DEQ Deliverable 5.1). - We evaluated different Networks and trained (and validated) and have now a Deep learning Model that does not need much hardware power and is therefore very performant.
Application Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The core consideration were to improve the safety of the workers. Therefore, we took various steps to increase the robustness of the system, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Testing different AI Models, using one of the most performant. o Using context analysis and object tracking to improve performance o Use Hardware, which can be used in an rough outdoor environment (and lock it). o Keep the system simple.
Security & Compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hardware is locked (and protected via key) - No data storage - No external interface except connection to IQS and ITK.
Performance Metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Since the last update (beginning of March) very stable - See results section (3.7)
Support & Maintenance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ongoing support, if problems occur.
Business Model & Pricing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Currently, we are in discussions about the pricing model with different stakeholders, among one industrialization partner from the machine manufacturer and several quarries and ready-mix concrete operators.
Competitive Advantage	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Due to the training of AI specifically for quarries and ready-mix concrete operators, we received the feedback from our partners that for this field of view and with that performance not many systems are usable.
Future Enhancements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The speed of development for (AI) applications is constantly increasing. As ITK has set-up an pipeline for AI development we hope to be able to provide our DEQ partners also in the future with the developments concerning AI. - It can be expected that the noise of the alert might be too quiet. Besides using a louder alert, it would be possible to develop a solution that sends directly a message to a device (e.g. smartphone or machine).

2.7.2 Activities performed since Novembre 2023

The following text passage is from Deliverable 5.1, where it is described:

Like VICAT a visit took place in September 2023 to discuss the possibility of a system expansion. In this context it turned out that for CIMPOR would be interested to monitor the area as shown in Figure 22 below and inform with an acoustic alert in case a person is detected (outside the vehicles) by the system.

Figure 22 Area system expansion

As the use cases, the requirements and the corresponding architecture are very much comparable to the prototype installed at the scraper plant, a lot of the already known software/hardware can be installed; it is currently running on an Basler Camera at the top of the conveyor has an acoustic alert (Backup and Reverse Warning Alarms) from Brigade an NVIDIA ORIN Board and a running Team-Viewer license (in order to check for ITK from abroad on the system and install e.g. updates.). In May 2024 the installation took place at CIMPOR. The field of view of the camera is displayed below.

The architecture of the system and the corresponding features does look like described in Figure 41:

The camera first detects a scene, then various AI models are being used (e.g. including one for object tracking) and then an acoustic alert is triggered informing the workers to not be present in that area. The amount of detected persons is sent via 3G to the IQS, where a counter of the detections is activated, giving constantly the operator the possibility to monitor safety indicators.

Figure 23: Current Field of View of the camera.

The AI algorithm for the CIMPOR installation was adapted and improved using a dedicated AI pipeline. This pipeline facilitated efficient data acquisition, labeling, training, and validation. New data was collected, capturing the specific environment, camera perspective, and potential hazard scenarios. This data was then labeled using established guidelines, ensuring high-quality ground truth for training the AI model.

Leveraging this new dataset, the object detection model was retrained. The training process incorporated data augmentation techniques to enhance the model's robustness and generalization capabilities. Performance was rigorously evaluated throughout the training process using relevant metrics (see also result section). This iterative process allowed for continuous optimization of the model and its hyperparameters. The resulting retrained model demonstrated significant improvement in object detection accuracy and a reduction in false negatives, enhancing the safety and reliability of the system at the CIMPOR site. The updated model was then deployed to the CIMPOR installation via an over-the-air update.

2.8 Environmental performance based on historical data (Task 5.4)

For each site, the environmental performance in over 30 environmental impact categories has been calculated using historical data from 2019. A model of the plant has been built in the online web platform, PlantSmith, where all products have been connected to consumption data for the year 2019. Background environmental models have then been used to estimate the environmental performance of each product group. The results have been presented in Deliverable 5.4 for the sites.

Figure 24: Environmental performance simulation

3 Results

3.1 Weighing scales

In a large-capacity crushing plant such as the one in this pilot quarry, any deviations from optimum working parameters immediately lead to losses and, consequently, costs of various kinds that are not recoverable when detected, bearing in mind that the process runs continuously and in a cascade.

In addition, we are working with natural resources that are therefore heterogeneous in nature and interfere with the performance of both mobile and fixed equipment.

Having perfect control of the amount of material fed to the crushing plant is essential in order to be able to in order to be able to adjust the working parameters in good time, maximising production and reducing energy consumption, equipment wear and environmental impacts.

Two sets of scales were installed. The first with three scales controls the feed to the crushing plant, and the sum of these three scales is the total amount of raw material discharged into the feeder. The second set of scales, totalling five, controls the amount of material discharged from the silos. As there are aggregate loading points in the plant that cannot be controlled by scales, the sum of the two sets is not the same.

Figure 25 Belt scales control.

Considering that the support structure for the conveyor belts had to be altered to allow the equipment to be coupled, and consequently the carpets had to be structurally reinforced at the installation sites. The scales consist of weighing equipment coupled to a roller support with a load cell, and a rubber mesh speed meter with a wheel which, through direct contact with a magnetic pulse meter, provides speed information.

Figure 26 one of the Scales installed in a conveyor belt.

Therefore, the first set of three scales is used to determine the quantity produced, considering that the amount of material remaining in the buffer stock is negligible considering the quantity produced each month.

In addition to the accumulated quantity produced, these scales also provide information on the instantaneous flow rate, operating time and speed of the conveyor belts.

Figure 27 Scales control equipment at CIMPOR's Alenquer quarry crushing plant.

The information generated by these scales is transmitted to Scada via a local area network that integrates this information with the remaining from the PLC that controls the crushing plant.

The information for the datalake is sent using a 4G modem, bearing in mind that the fixed internal data communication network is not yet active. However, there is already a fibre optic network on site. This process has taken longer considering the existing network security criteria in place at the company. A firewall has been installed to allow data to be transmitted over the fibre optic network to the datalake, which is now being configured.

From the moment these scales were installed, it was possible to obtain information that was crucial to the operation of the crushing plant, allowing its operation to be optimized, with emphasis on:

1. it allows the correct adjustment of the crushing equipment, particularly the primary crusher, in order to distribute the crushed material correctly. This is particularly important because the screen subsequent to the primary crusher consists of 3 decks with progressively smaller screen openings and it is necessary to ensure correct distribution across all of them;
2. it allows the assessment of the influence that the blasting has on the particle size distribution, since by maintaining the adjustment of the crusher fixed it is possible to understand the distribution of material across the 3 belts that together make up the total feed. This is particularly important considering that 1 of the belts (T1) corresponds to the feed cleaning material, with smaller granulometry and clays;
3. the correct quantification of the feed allows the calculation of indicators related to performance and energy consumption to be correctly calculated and followed. If these indicators are reliable, it is possible to react more quickly and reliably in order to correct errors in the operation or regulation of equipment;
4. allows the release of indicators for controlling upstream equipment and evaluating its performance, as well as assisting in its sizing. It should be noted that this information contributed to supporting the selection and purchase of rock loading and transportation equipment that took place in 2024.

3.2 Mobile equipment sensors

Considering the work environment, namely the fact that it is an open space with approximately 70ha of working area, in weather conditions where sometimes the visibility is reduced, the existence of a tool where it is possible in almost real time to have a general comprehension of the location of the machines as such major indicators on their operation is an aid that can increase significantly the optimization of the equipment, with major return on profitability, energy savings and safety.

Although the most recent equipment already has telematic systems that allow you to remotely obtain information about its use, this information essentially refers to mechanical performance, i.e. consumption, operating times, failures and speeds. Furthermore, these tools are manufacturer specific, so the need to have a tool that incorporates all machines regardless of the manufacturer is obvious.

The About system implemented with its plug and play facility allows all these equipment to be easily integrated under the same platform.

Figure 28 Plug and play unit to install in the mobile equipment.

The equipment was installed on quarry trucks, aggregate trucks and loaders. The ease of installation allowed the machine sensors to be changed during the course of the project whenever there was a change in the fleet, motivated by new acquisitions or prolonged maintenance periods.

In addition to all the metrics mentioned above, it is worth noting that the use of machines can be tracked. This fact is particularly important as it allows for retro-analysis of the operation. The following aspects stand out in particular: it allows analysis of the routes taken by the equipment; and record loading and unloading points.

Figure 29 Example of loading and unloading points in the quarry plant.

The recording of loading and unloading points proved to be very useful, particularly in order to be able to carry out the appropriate analysis of deviations in product quality. This aspect is particularly important in an activity such as the extractive industry where the quality of the raw material is quite heterogeneous, thus allowing for a deeper understanding of the reserves and adequate planning for the advancement of exploitation.

On the other hand, recording the routes taken allows the equipment to be optimised, minimising bottlenecks, reducing the distance travelled and consequently fuel consumption and ensuring that the routes taken are as efficient as possible whilst simultaneously maintaining high levels of health and safety.

From an environmental point of view, it has also proven to be important, considering that during the dry season it is necessary to sprinkle water on the circulation routes to avoid dust emissions, and in this way, knowing the exact transport circuits, it is possible to concentrate water consumption where it is strictly necessary. This aspect is particularly important considering the effort the company makes to reduce its impacts and because it is located in a region where there is often a lack of rainfall.

3.3 ICT Platform

At the Cimpor site, a data management platform (CDMP) utilizing data lake technologies has been deployed and is operational (<https://cdmp.cimpor.confidencial.eu/>). This platform collects daily data from various quarry processes, including automation (Scada), environment, health & safety (H&S), mobile machinery and IoT for AI Service. These data are accessible to users and expert systems.

Data from the Scada system is collected by a dedicated service, enabling the generation of dashboards for monitoring quarry productivity KPI (rates, index, etc.). Data from the mobile machineries is collected by a dedicated service, allowing the tracking of machine KPI (cycles, consumption, distance, etc.). Data from the H&S system is collected by a dedicated service, facilitating the monitoring of safety indicators. Data from the Plantsmith system is collected by a dedicated service, enabling the tracking of environmental performance across over 30 impact categories.

All data are accessible through a unique Application deployed in the Azure cloud. These tools break down data silos and facilitate data integration from diverse sources, enhancing decision-making capabilities and performance monitoring as shown below in these Business Management Tools of the IQS.

Figure 30 Business Management Tools of the IQS

Finally in the context of Cimpor we developed the main use case leveraging IoT technologies in DEQ. The deployed IoT platform connects the dust and water sensors in the site with the data lake and the forecast AI services. IoT data can be used in real-time or later using the data lake IoT data browser developed within the CDMF. The data lake browser creates a dynamic catalogue with a front-end, a back-end, and a REST API. The successful integration of real-time data from dust sensors demonstrated that the IQS is capable of integrating with any IoT device.

These results demonstrate the successful implementation of the IQS project concept. This concept is highly adaptable for integrating new indicators useful for quarry management and facilitating decision-making mechanisms.

3.4 AI Algorithms

Extractive activity in general and quarrying in particular are based on the processing of natural resources that are inherently heterogeneous, in an uncontrolled environment exposed to atmospheric agents. This aspect conditions the planning of work and the performance of the activity.

In the case in question, atmospheric conditions, namely temperature, wind and rain, have a direct impact on production, both in terms of quantity and quality, and on environmental impacts.

The set of sensors strategically placed around the perimeter of the quarry, which allow for the continuous analysis of several relevant weather parameters, not only provide instant information necessary for daily management, but also provide essential information for creating robust models that allow for anticipatory reactions.

Figure 31 Sensor for dust measurement.

Figure 32 Weather station.

The real-time availability of atmospheric data and in particular dust concentration data allows for more efficient management of water spraying to reduce dust emissions. This is particularly important considering that the quarry is located in an area where there are houses around its perimeter and where the internal circulation routes are not paved.

This management, in addition to the obvious reduction in environmental impacts, allows for significant savings in water and fuel, since water is sprayed using a tanker truck. Therefore, it has a direct positive impact on cost savings in the operation.

Figure 33 Information collected in real time from the dust sensors.

3.5 BIM Integration

3.5.1 General Summary

Building Information Modeling (BIM) strategies were comprehensively implemented at CIMPOR Alenquer to support the quarry's lifecycle management through advanced digital tools. Detailed 3D BIM models of the treatment plant and site topography were developed, utilizing available drawings, drone data, and site photos, and prepared in IFC format. A long-term 4D BIM plan was created in Asta Powerproject, simulating the quarry's documentation, preparation, exploitation, and restoration phases, incorporating resource allocation and calculating activity durations based on volumes derived from the models. Complementing this, a detailed short-term mass haulage study was conducted to optimize resource utilization, presented through time-location diagrams and histograms. Quantitative schedule risk analysis, following DCMA standards, was performed to provide probabilistic insights into the project timeline. Furthermore, a 7D model-based Common Data Environment (CDE) was deployed using Autodesk Tandem, integrating the BIM model with static asset data and dynamic mobile machinery data from the DataLake, offering a valuable platform for monitoring and management.

3.5.2 Activities performed

Following the detailed development reported in Deliverable D4.5, the activities for CIMPOR Alenquer focused on the finalization, deployment, and handover of the comprehensive BIM solutions:

- **BIM Model & 4D Plan Finalization:** The detailed 3D BIM models (treatment plant, topography, volumes) and the associated long-term 4D BIM plan (including exploitation and restoration phases) were finalized and prepared for deployment. The results of the detailed short-term mass haulage study and the quantitative schedule risk analysis were also compiled.
- **CDE Deployment and Data Integration:** The Common Data Environment (CDE) platform (Autodesk Tandem) was deployed for CIMPOR. This included uploading the finalized BIM model, incorporating static asset data, and establishing the connection with the central DataLake via the custom integrator. This enabled the visualization of available dynamic mobile machinery data linked to the assets within the CDE.
- **Training and Handover:** The CIMPOR team received access to the CDE platform and associated deliverables (4D simulation, risk analysis reports). Initial support and guidance were provided to facilitate the use of the CDE for visualizing the plant and integrated operational data.

3.6 KPI definition

Considering the volume of data that is generated, it is necessary to define variables that robustly and simply portray the unfolding of the activity. In the specific case of this pilot quarry, as it is an operation where the volume of raw material processed and the quantity of resources used is significant, any deviations or delayed corrections have significant impacts. This control is only possible through the definition of KPIs that allow for a snapshot at a glance.

The creation of dashboards where this information is available is an essential tool for managing operations, and a way for the company to communicate internally in a concise manner without losing information.

Figure 34 KPI for plant utilisation

Figure 35 KPI for plant maintenance

3.7 Development of H&S systems for stationary equipment (Task 5.1 and 5.2)

Having safety identified as one of the core objectives of DEQ we have installed here an AI based system that informs the direct involved workers and the operators via a dashboard when they are walking around in an area, where no person should be present.

In general, when interpreting the performance of AI one must balance certain KPI scores. Here a short insertion about the logic behind it. Below in Table 1 Different classes. you see the different classes. On the left side “predicted class” means detected by the AI and on the top, “actual class” means ground truth (reality).

Of course, the worst case, is a false negative, meaning that our AI system did not recognize the person, despite the fact that there is a person. Yet, too many false positives, meaning that there is an alert despite the fact that there is no person lowers the acceptance of the system.

Table 1 Different classes.

	Actual CLASS		
Predicted CLASS		True	False
	True	True Positives	False Positives (No person but alert)
	False	False Negatives (Person, but not alert)	True Negatives

In the field of AI, one often talks about “Thresholds”, meaning that how sure is the AI when detecting/classifying an object that this object is also there. Now the fine-tuning starts. For instance, if one recognizes a high level of false positives one

can decrease the threshold on the costs that there will be an increase in false negatives. Currently we are working with a threshold of above 90%.

In this context, two valuable indicators for the performance of an AI algorithm are precision and recall. Precision answers the question of what percentage of the positive results predicted by the model are true positives. It helps to understand the proportion of true positives out of all predicted positive results (i.e., true positives and false positives).

Recall provides information about how many actual positive instances were correctly detected by the model. It is related to false negatives and true positives, not true negatives. Recall estimates the proportion of relevant positive instances that were detected.

Again, based on the idea of balancing, if one wants to increase recall, this will often come at the cost of precision (and vice versa). For both indicators, we have found reasonable balances, with both values above 90%.

The indicators are based per frame. Currently we are running on, depending on the setting, more than 10 frames per second. As we have some reaction time (and in order to decrease false positives), we defined, that there must be a detection for an object across four consecutive frames.

In general focussing on the performance of the AI and the system we are satisfied. Yet there are for further industrialization improvements to be made:

- 1) More Test and Validation needs to be carried out. Despite that we tested different corner cases and have good results in practise, more rigorous testing needs to be carried out here.
- 2) For our first PoC in Parsberg we used with the MultiSense S30 a different time, which was by the time nearly 10 times more expensive than the Basler Camera installed at CIMPOR. However, over the time the price of the MultiSense dropped considerably and we observe a much better performance by the MultiSense S30.
- 3) See above concerning the feature, informing the machine operators and the person walking around via additional devices.

4 Impact assessment

The results obtained throughout the project, particularly in this final phase, were the result of a joint effort by multidisciplinary teams. It is a fact that for the pilot quarry resulting from the competitive framework there are many very important aspects that are often relegated to the second place.

The opportunity to work alongside project partners, with highly competent, motivated and knowledgeable teams at the forefront of their fields of expertise, brought to the field a fantastic opportunity to develop and implement technology and knowledge in the quarrying activity.

In a highly competitive world where digitalization is increasingly an integral part of everyday life, it is essential that this activity does not miss any opportunity to evolve. Digitalization in quarries not only brings immediate economic benefits, taking into account greater process control, but also brings environmental and occupational health and safety benefits, which are fundamental for an activity that is essential for the development of societies.

As this is an activity with environmental impacts, the opportunity to develop cutting-edge technologies and methods that can contribute to any minimization and improvement of society's perception is of extreme importance.

The learning carried out and the experiences acquired should be disseminated through the activity in order to amplify the benefits achieved as well as continue a process of continuous improvement.

5 Future

The technologies developed within DigiEcoQuarry align fully with sustainability objectives, contributing to resource optimisation, reductions in energy consumption, and the minimisation of environmental impacts, all while improving worker safety. The replicability of this model in other quarries, both within the same corporate group and across external companies, is highly feasible, as the solutions have been designed specifically to address the unique challenges of the extractive sector—challenges that are not typically considered in generic commercial applications.

In conclusion, the project has laid a solid foundation for the effective digital transformation of the mining industry, demonstrating that the combination of advanced technologies with sector-specific operational knowledge can generate significant benefits in terms of efficiency, safety, and sustainability.

6 Conclusions

The technologies developed within the DigiEcoQuarry project have enabled CIMPOR to make significant progress in its digital transformation, adapting cutting-edge innovations to the sector's technical, economic, and environmental requirements. Through specifically designed tools and protocols aimed at optimising daily operations, substantial improvements have been achieved in decision-making processes and access to information.

Since the pilot projects involved end users directly, their feedback has been instrumental in evaluating the impact of the project. To systematically collect their opinions, the project management team conducted surveys and interviews with quarry managers, ensuring an accurate and objective assessment. The gathered information has been consolidated in this report and shared with project partners, facilitating knowledge transfer and allowing the achievements to be capitalised upon.

In the case of CIMPOR, the implementation of these technologies has been positively received, particularly in terms of structuring information across the entire operation within a single integrated system. This has provided management and workers with a near real-time, comprehensive view of operations, improving efficiency and reducing costs and complications associated with data fragmentation. Previously, the focus on isolated processes hindered operational and strategic decision-making due to a lack of readily accessible data offering a holistic perspective.

A particularly significant advancement has been the improvement in data generation and accessibility for regulatory reporting and dashboard creation. The increasing demand for documentation from public authorities and stakeholders has made structured and reliable information an essential requirement. The new system enables both internal and external personnel to efficiently access historical data that reflects the actual operational conditions of the quarry. Another indirect yet highly valuable benefit has been the improved communication with the local community, thanks to the availability of structured and easily accessible environmental data.

Another key benefit has been the near real-time monitoring of mobile equipment in operation, which has significantly reduced response times to incidents that could affect production or safety.

The CIMPOR pilot has also integrated advanced technologies for monitoring environmental and atmospheric conditions, allowing for efficient water consumption management and the adaptation of operations to daily climatic variations. Previously, operational decisions were based on historical data with broad temporal resolutions (every four years) or on imprecise estimates. The deployment of networked sensors now makes it possible to adjust water use based on georeferenced data with hourly granularity, optimising its application for dust suppression, road maintenance, and overall environmental management.

Additionally, the incorporation of geolocation systems has greatly enhanced safety by analysing the interactions between machinery and workers, allowing for the identification and mitigation of high-risk zones. This has enabled the automatic georeferenced marking of restricted-access areas within the facilities and the optimisation of site layouts to reduce future hazards—an aspect of particular importance given the challenges of managing large-scale areas. As part of the zonal alert system, a combination of acoustic notifications and electronic messages has been implemented, allowing for more effective management of warnings in environments with high noise levels.

The introduction of mobile equipment monitoring has exceeded expectations, enabling the verification of transport routes and the optimisation of fuel consumption. A historical record of geolocated data has been created, which will facilitate more precise future analyses and allow operational strategies to be adjusted for more efficient transport scenarios. One particularly important aspect has been the ability to digitalise existing machinery rather than having to purchase new sensor-equipped equipment. Throughout the DEQ implementation, CIMPOR's management team has recognised the critical importance of consolidating data generated by mobile machinery into a single system. Avoiding vendor lock-in and

eliminating data fragmentation across various manufacturers' platforms ensures comprehensive access to operational data.

With regard to fixed installations, the ability to break down energy consumption by section and/or zone has been a major step forward. Previously, the lack of granular measurement and an organised historical record of data made it difficult to identify opportunities for improvement. Now, having a detailed historical dataset by zone has enabled impact assessments and provided justification for investments in energy efficiency. In this context, the integration of data from weighing scales has been particularly relevant, as these devices play a crucial role in technical and economic calculations. However, ensuring the robustness of these devices for operation in harsh environments is essential, guaranteeing their resilience against impacts and extreme conditions.

One of the primary challenges identified has been the learning curve associated with introducing digital data management technologies into a sector that has traditionally been slow to embrace digitalisation. Nonetheless, the experience gained during the project has led to the development of intuitive and user-friendly solutions that, with minimal customisation, can be effectively implemented in other quarries.

The centralisation of data through tools such as data lakes and data warehouses has demonstrated its potential to enhance decision-making, reduce uncertainty in future optimizations and enable effective environmental and health & safety monitoring. However, widespread adoption of these technologies across the sector will require increased awareness and dedicated training for workers to ensure their practical impact extends beyond just technical teams.

To maximise the project's long-term impact, it is recommended that efforts continue towards integrating these technologies into operational processes, with a particular focus on leveraging mobile devices. Digitalisation through portable devices will facilitate deployment, updates, and usability, ensuring broad adoption across the industry. However, it is crucial to take into account the connectivity limitations inherent to mining environments and adapt solutions accordingly.

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